

“Importance of Training Staff in Modern Workplace Era”

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ABSTRACT

This paper analyze extent of importance of training staff in modern workplace era among workers of Ansec Human Resources Services PvtLtd with thought of gender, age and skill variation. Training is the developing in oneself or others, teaching any skills and knowledge or fitness which relate to specific useful competencies. Staff training is the process of training the current staff of business, company or organization for increasing profitability or productivity of the organization. This is very important as it can help in professional development for career development of employee and ultimately for the betterment of the organization.

Key Words: Human Resource, Staffing, Workplace, Training, Employee

1. INTRODUCTION

A firm's primary source of gaining a competitive advantage over competitor companies is founded upon the knowledge and skills its inducted employees and stakeholders possess and bring to the company as assets. Employees' abilities and skills as well as specialty are highlighted for the purposes of enabling them to work with increased efficiency and dedication. These abilities can be enhanced to ensure that the elements of efficiency and dedication are maintained. This enhancement of

employees' abilities can be done through training programs that among other benefits, motivate employees to perform at the best of their abilities. By utilizing the being of long-term planning and investing in training programs and new training techniques, the employees of an organization and other internal stakeholders tend to respond better to uncertain circumstances that may occur in the future, and as such, the performance showcased by the entirety of the workforce may be observed to increase. For this reason, for workers to perform their responsibilities in the best possible manner, organizations more often than not utilize the different training techniques for the purposes of boosting the employees' performance potential. The moment employees grow the perception that the company values them as efficient and dedicated employees, they tend to respond with improved performance in their duties thereby helping the organization achieve its objectives and overall goal. This case study assesses how employee training is necessary for a company such as Ansec Human resource Services and identifies the possible benefits that could result from utilizing different training techniques. Employees are not only responsible for the creation and actualization of a product, but also the provision of related services to customers.

2. MEANING AND DEFINITION OF TRAINING

Training is one of the main part of Human Resource Development. It is mainly concerned with enhancing a specific skill to a desired standard by instruction and practice. Training is the important tool which is useful for employee which mean it can bring an employee which mean it can bring an employee into position where they can do their job correctly and efficiently. Training is the act of enhancing knowledge and skilled employee for doing particular job.

2.1. Definition of Training:

The organized procedures by which people or employee learn knowledge and/or skill for a definite purpose. Training refers to the teaching and learning activities carried on for the primary goal of helping members of an organization or company acquire and apply the knowledge, skills, abilities, and attitudes needed by a particular job.

2.2. Need for Training:

Each association ought to give preparing to all the representatives independent of their capabilities and abilities.

Explicitly the requirement for preparing emerges as a result of following reasons:

1. Motorization, computerization, and mechanization have brought about numerous progressions that require prepared staff having enough abilities. The association should prepare the representatives to enhance them with the most recent innovation and information.

2. Authoritative unpredictability:

With present day developments, innovative up gradation, and diversification the greater part of the associations have gotten mind boggling. This has exasperated the issues of coordination. In this way, so as to adapt up to the complexities, preparing has gotten compulsory.

3. Human connection

Each administration needs to keep up awesome human relations, and this has made preparing as one of the fundamental conditions to manage human issues.

4. To coordinate worker details with the activity necessities and authoritative needs:

A worker's particular may not actually suit to the necessities of the activity and the association, independent of past experience and abilities. There is constantly a hole between a worker's current particulars and the association's necessities. For filling this hole preparing is required.

5. Change in the activity task: Training is likewise vital when the current representative is expert moted to the more elevated level or moved to another office. Preparing is additionally required to outfit the old representatives with new methods and innovations.

3. IMPORTANCE OF TRAINING:

Preparing factor, the organization or any association couldn't be finished the objective or they neglect to improve the efficiency .It is a significant action of Human Resource Development which helps in upgrading the competency of representatives. Preparing gives a ton of advantages to the workers, for example, improvement in productivity and adequacy, advancement of fearlessness and helps each one in self-administration. The strength and progress of the association consistently relies upon the preparation bestowed to the representatives. Preparing gets essential under every single step of development and enhancement. No one but preparing can improve or expand the quality and diminish the wastages to the base. Preparing and improvement is likewise fundamental to adjust as per changing condition Training of workers and troughs are significant right now and without.

3.1. Types of Training:

Different kinds of preparing can be given to the representatives, for example, enlistment preparing, boost preparing, hands on preparing, vestibule preparing, and preparing for advancements.

1. Acceptance preparing:

Otherwise called direction preparing given for the newcomers so as to cause them to acclimate with the interior condition of an association. It causes the workers to comprehend the methods, set of principles, approaches existing in that association.

2. Employment guidance preparing:

This preparation gives an outline about the activity and experienced mentors exhibits the whole occupation. Expansion preparing is offered to representatives in the wake of assessing their presentation if vital.

3. Vestibule preparing:

It is the preparation on genuine work to be finished by a representative yet led away from the work place.

Boost preparing:

1. This kind of preparing is offered so as to fuse the most recent advancement in a specific field. This preparation is granted to overhaul the abilities of

representatives. This preparation can likewise be utilized for advancing a representative.

5. Apprenticeship preparing:

Apprentice is a worker who spends a prescribed period of time under a supervisor.

Importance of Staff Training

Human asset is one of the most essential segments of an association and might be seen as the foundation of each foundation or association as a significant asset. Thus, associations put to a great extent in the human asset capital under the understanding that the exhibition of human asset at last increases the presentation and profitability of the association. Preparing presents associations and the administration of these associations with prime chances to extend the information base of their workers and advantages representatives in some of the way.

4.LITERATURE REVIEW

For any organization or business that targets improved productivity and organizational efficiency, staff training ought to be part of the operating strategies of the organization. Staff training is a vital component since through it, employees are developed towards the long-term objectives with which the organization identifies (Anthony, 1999). AnsecHuman resources services assesses work capabilities of individuals as aligned by job function and provides a wide range of training and development opportunities to employees for the purposes of nurturing all employees into better performer in their fields or respective areas of expertise. The company

provides its employees with access to comparable training programs including those based overseas regardless of their location or placement. To ensure this, the company has set up a mobile education system and a global education. Despite the initial costs an organization invests, staff training pays back the investment costs in multiples. This chapter focuses on the literature on staff training, training needs analysis and the manner in which training is designed and delivered in an organizational concept. Current training and development practices are discussed as well as the emerging trends in staff training in organizations in the contemporary world.

This literature review is comprehensive rather than selective. It seeks to among other issues, address the historical background of training and leadership training in addition to the theories and concepts that regard staff training and development. It also focuses on the importance attached to training and management development as well as training design and methods alongside pre-training and post-training environments, training needs analysis and to a lesser extent, on trainee characteristics and training evaluation. Recent developments in the theories and concepts that regard training and management development include cognitive learning theories, team training, high technology training methods and, more importantly, on-the-job managerial development as in management development. Staff training has been identified to provide solutions to a number of manpower issues that are seen to influence optimum productivity rather Included in these problems are operating problems. These problems emerge in any groups including the skilled and unskilled, line and staff, professional and paraprofessional as well as the lower, middle and upper management stakeholder slots. Although these problems differ in nature, they all have a common denominator which stands as the solution to their appreciative backgrounds. Among the problems to which staff training and development is a solution includes the needs to develop new skills, attitudes, understanding and knowledge; reduce waste, turnover, absenteeism, accidents, lateness and overhead costs; implementation of novel or enhanced policies or regulations; fight obsolescence in methods, products, skills, markets, capital management, and technologies among other aspects; develop replacements, improve the deployment of human resources, prepare manpower for advancement, and ensure leadership continuity; as well as the need to ensure the survival and overall growth of the organization.

5.OBJECTIVES

1. To investigate the importance of training staff in workplace.
2. To raise productivity and efficiency of employee and the organization as a whole.
3. To give knowledge about new and innovative techniques of work performance.
4. To enhance potentialities for career development of employee.

6.RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

6.1. Research design

Research design is the procedure used to collect, gather and analyze data, interpret results and for which findings can be determined and disseminated. A research design can be qualitative, quantitative or a combination of both designs (mixed method). Qualitative design, as a research design, is majorly subjective and features a naturalistic and interpretive approach through which data is collected using interviews and other individual based methods such as focus groups for the purpose of generating qualitative data. On the other hand, quantitative design, unlike qualitative design, is majorly objective and features collection of data in form of numbers for which statistical methods can be used to test hypotheses. The importance of training staff in the modern workplace era and how an organizational success is impacted by staff training can be measured using various quantitative and qualitative methods.

6.2. Convenience Sampling:

In Convenience sampling, sample is taken from the cluster of individual and it's a kind of non-likelihood sampling methodology. Its conjointly referred to as grab sampling, accidental sampling or chance sampling. This sort of sampling is most helpful for pilot testing. It's a kind of non-likelihood sampling methodology wherever the sample is taken from a majority of individuals. This sort of sampling is most helpful for pilot testing, pilot testing may be a conductan attempt before actual.

6.3. Data Collection

The purpose of analysis was explained to the workers and form were administered to them.

1. **Primary Data:** information is 1st hand information, this information collected from employees, managers etc. by conducting the form having one on one interaction with workers.
2. **Sampling Size:** A survey of one hundred workers operating within the organization provided the info base for this study.

7. LIMITATION

Although the research attained its objectives and aims, there existed some unavoidable shortcomings or limitations. This section recognizes some of the limitations and shortcomings involved in the research process. First off, the study was limited to a choice of data collection as in secondary data was the only source of information; as such, it deprived the research of obtaining raw data from interviews and questionnaires. Integration of additional data collection methods such as primary data collection could otherwise have increased the research depth as well as scope, therefore, precipitating to a more credible research.

In this light, the researcher did not have a chance to examine the impact of staff training on the organizational success of other companies that are not technology-based. In addition, the study cannot affirm that implementing the aspect of staff training could possibly have the same effect on other companies as in Samsung.

Lastly, the lack of past studies on the same topic acted as a limitation to the research. Despite previous studies having been conducted on the importance of training staff.

8.ANALYSIS AND DATA INTERPRETATION

Q. 1.How long have you been working in this company?

Table No. 1

Particulars	No. of employees
Less than year	15
1 to 3 years	35
3 to 5 years	30
Above 5 years	20

Graph no. 1

Interpretation:

Here 20% employees have worked more than 5 years as they are the most experienced employees in the company,30% employee have worked between 3 to 5 years,35% employee have worked 1 to 3 years and 15% employee have worked less than a year.

Q. 2. Do you know the importance of training staff and is it necessary for the company?

Table no. 2

Particulars	No. of employees
Agree	55
Disagree	5
Strongly agree	20
Strongly disagree	10
Neutral	10

Graph No. 2

Interpretation:

55% employees are agree with it, 20% employees are strongly agree, 5% are disagree, 10% employees are strongly disagree, 10% employees are neutral.

Q. 3. How many training programme have you attend last year?

Table No. 3

Particulars	No. of employees
0	7
1	33
2	35
3	25

Graph No. 3

Interpretation:

46% of employee have attend 2 times training programme in a year, 43% of employee have attend 3 times training programme, 9% of the employee have attend 1 training programme and 2% of employee they didn't attend any training programme.

Q. 4. Please rank the methods of training of your concern?

Table No. 4

Particulars	No. of employees
Job instruction training	15
Project based training	10
Executive leadership training	10
Class room training	45
Computer based training	20

Graph No. 4

Interpretation:

Above graph shows the rank which bases on the methods of training i.e. 45% employee have given their preference to class room training, 15% of the employee give their preference to job instruction training, 20% of the employee give their preference to computer based training 10% of employee give their preference to project based training and executive leadership training.

Q. 5. How often you are being sent to training?

Table No. 5

Particulars	No. of employees
Weekly	15
Monthly	55
Quarterly	5
Half yearly	15
Annually	10

Graph No. 5

Interpretation:

55% of employee have sent to training once in a month, 15% of employee have sent to training once in a week and quarterly, 15% employee have sent to training half yearly and 5% employee sent to training annually.

Q. 6. Percentage of total employee cost allocated for training.

Table No. 6

Particulars	No. of employees
Less than 1% of budget	15
Around 1% to 2%	25
Around 3% to 5%	40
More than 5%	20

Graph No. 6

Interpretation:

40% of the employee cost is allocated for training which is maximum which is around 3-5%, 25% of the employee cost allocated for training is 1-2%, 20% of the employee cost for training is more than 5% and 15% employee cost is less than 1%.

9.FINDINGS

1. It is observed that maximum respondent are aware about the importance of training staff and they attend maximum training programmes.
2. Employee are aware as they have attend 1,2,3 training programmes.
3. A significant number of respondent agree that training gives opportunity to aquire the skill
4. Maximum respondent agree that training programme helps in their personal development and also organizational development.
5. Majority of the respondent are agree that organization allocate right person for the training and invest maximum employee cost for training
6. Some of the respondents are not attending the training program as they don't have that awareness about importance of training programmes.

10. SUGGESTION

1. Greater awareness of the objectives of the trainingand development programmes must be created among the trainees at the time of their nomination for the training so that it helps the trainee easily understand and attain the objectives and goals of the programmes.
2. Training programmes must be conducted at the frequent intervals to help the workers update with new techniques and improve their performance.
3. Organization must take efforts to see that trainees are provided with the best of facilities bringing in new improvement with every training programme.
4. Training programmes must be given importance according to the expectations of the employee.
5. Entertainment programmes should be undertake during the training periods in order to reduce stress of the trainee.

11. CONCLUSION

The main source of gaining a competitive advantage for a company over competitor companies is founded upon the knowledge and skills its stakeholders possess. These skills and knowledge are viewed as assets since it is through their manifestation that organizational performance and success is achieved along with employee retention and low employee turnover. The abilities and specialties that employees identify with are noticed through the efforts engaged by companies to enable employees to work with the required levels of efficiency. Training and development processes are engaged to enhance abilities and skills for the purposes of maintaining the productive elements of efficacy and dedication. As such, for workers to perform their responsibilities in the best possible manner, organizations more often than not utilize the different training techniques for the purposes of boosting the employees' performance potential. In cases where employees are put through training programs

the overall performance may not reach the full potential thus proving a disadvantage to the company in question. The primary reason behind the aforementioned disadvantage is the mere fact that if their skills are not honed or polished, employees tend to be unaware of what they lack or is missing in their working techniques and if no training is given to them, they may not be able to improve on their weaknesses, strengths and the needed skills. For any given firm that is part of any sector of the economy, it is important that the working force is well motivated and can carry out duties efficiently in most condition.

12.REFERENCES

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